

The Influence of Microeconomic Variables: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the map of research developments regarding the influence of microeconomic variables. The research was conducted from 1982 to 2022 by searching national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Sinta, and Scopus via the Perish/Harzing application, with the keyword "Microeconomics". Based on the search results, there were 323 research articles, which were then input into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a Library Research study. Research result shows that the number of publications has increased significantly every year. And based on the mapping results using the VOSviewer application, research regarding the influence of Microeconomic variables is divided into 7 clusters and 154 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of the Library Research study, there are 2 main themes surrounding the influence of microeconomic variables.

Keywords: Microeconomics; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research

Introduction

The economy is a system that regulates how the resources available in a country, such as labor, capital and raw materials, are used to meet human needs and desires. The economy is an important factor for the survival of a country because a healthy economy can improve people's welfare, create jobs, and strengthen political stability and security of a country. Apart from that, the economy can also influence the growth and development of a country, as well as help that country to compete in the global arena. Economics also has other roles, namely as a measure of economic growth, measuring inflation, measuring a country's unemployment rate, helping to understand and manage international trade, and helping to manage public policy. The economy is the pulse point of a country, this is the basis for a country to be said to be a developed country if its economic growth is good, technology is developing and infrastructure is well developed, so that it can support economic growth and progress.

Economics is the study of how individuals and societies make choices regarding the use of available resources, such as natural resources, capital, and people. In economics, we learn about how people make decisions with various associated consequences. Individual decisions are combined become the people's choice. Economics is also a behavioral science or social science that discusses how individuals, companies, or society fulfill their needs through various available choices, such as primary, secondary, and tertiary needs. Companies also have to make choices about what goods to produce, to whom to distribute the production results, or what goods will be consumed by society. These various problems are related to how to fulfill, produce and distribute goods and services, whether these goods are economic goods or public goods. Economics also deals with economic systems, such as market systems or socialist systems, and how they interact with factors such as prices, income, and consumption. Apart from that, economics also discusses how the government can influence the economy by using tools such as taxes, subsidies and regulations (Zahara & Anwar, 2020). Economics is also divided into two, namely macro and micro economics.

Economic progress cannot be separated from the role of microeconomics, one of which is MSMEs. This is in line with previous research put forward by (Anggraeni, 2022), MSMEs are considered to have become a sector that is able to compete and

become business actors that are tough and competitive in economic growth. Indonesia itself is a developing country dominated by micro, small and medium enterprises. According to the Ministry of Cooperatives MSMEs: 2018 in Arfah it was recorded that 99.99% of all business actors in Indonesia were dominated by MSME businesses which can make a major contribution to improving the regional economy. One way to introduce MSME products in society requires urgent marketing carried out by every MSME actor so that local products can be used directly by the wider community, not only marketed locally, nationally, even through international marketing (Arfah, 2022).

Scientific publications regarding Microeconomics also continue to increase from year to year based on searches via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Even in 2022, there will be 62 studies regarding Microeconomics. This shows that the development of microeconomic research is very rapid. The aim of this research is to map research topics around Microeconomics, especially Microeconomics in Indonesia over a period of 40 years. Researchers provide a fairly long time span, hoping that the data obtained will be more valid and accurate. In this research, the data was processed using: (1) Bibliometric studies, the VOSviewer bibliometric method was used to analyze and study maps of literature development in a scientific field, especially in scientific publications; and (2) Library Research studies are used to examine, recognize and review articles from accredited national journals, Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research can explain all research topics regarding Microeconomics. This can be a reference material for other researchers who wish to research microeconomics. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics regarding Microeconomics in Indonesia which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can be used as references for future researchers.

Literature Review

Microeconomics in summary is a branch of economics that studies the behavior of individuals, families and companies in making economic decisions and how these decisions affect the market (Sukirno, 2005). Microeconomics studies how individuals and companies make decisions regarding production, consumption and investment, as well as how decisions This affects the price and quantity of goods available on the market. Microeconomics also studies how individual and corporate decisions affect demand and supply in markets, as well as how the interaction between demand and supply affects the prices of goods. Microeconomics also discusses market structures, such as monopoly, oligopoly, and perfectly competitive markets, and how these market structures influence individual and company decisions (Zahara & Anwar, 2020).

Microeconomic theory was originally developed by classical scientists in the 18th century. Micro comes from the Greek word. Micros, meaning small. Micro theory does not mean that price theory is small or unimportant. Microeconomic theory often receives greater attention than macroeconomic theory. Microeconomics talks about individual units such as companies and households allocating their income to purchase various goods and services. The scope of Microeconomics is to study the economic activities of each economic unit, such as: (a) Interactions in the goods market. The market is defined as a meeting or relationship between demand and supply or a meeting between sellers and buyers of goods in large quantities. to create a certain price. For example, rice market, car market, electronics market; (b) Behavior of sellers and buyers Both sellers and buyers have a rational nature, namely where the seller wants maximum profit (maximum profit) while the buyer wants maximum satisfaction (maximum utility); (c) Interaction in the production factor market. From the buyer's side (consumers) have production factors and need money to meet their needs, while sellers (producers) have goods for human needs and need production factors by buying them. From this relationship, it can be seen that consumers and producers have a reciprocal relationship or need each other (Khusaini, 2013).

Bibliometrics is a technique used to analyze and measure scientific publications, including journals, books and conferences. Bibliometrics can be used

to evaluate research performance and scientific developments in a field. Bibliometric metrics can include number of publications, price index, impact factor, and number of citations (Jena et al., 2012). Bibliometrics can also be used to measure individual performance, such as measuring the number of publications and citations of a researcher. Bibliometrics can be used to assess the performance of research institutions and universities, as well as to compare research performance between countries. However, bibliometrics is not always an appropriate measure of research quality, as other factors such as originality and impact of the research must also be considered (Dubyna et al., 2022).

VOSviewer is software that can be used to display and analyze scientific publication data, such as journals, books and conferences. This software can help present publication data in visual form, such as a VOS (Viewer of Science) diagram that shows the relationship between keywords and collaboration between researchers. VOSviewer can also be used to analyze citation data and display information about the number of citations, impact factors, and price indices. This software can also be used to create bibliometric reports that show individual or institutional research performance (Nurul & Winoto, 2022). VOSviewer is freely available to use, and can be downloaded from the software's official website (van Eck NJ, 2022).

A Library Research is a review of existing literature in a research field. The purpose of a Library Research is to identify and evaluate existing sources so that they can provide an overview of research that has been conducted previously and help determine the direction of further research. Library Researchs can also help identify gaps or deficiencies in research that has been conducted previously, so that it can become a basis for conducting more meaningful and useful research. Library Researchs can be done by searching for and reading sources related to the research topic, such as scientific journals, books and conferences. Then, these sources can be grouped and analyzed to evaluate the contribution of each source to the research topic (Ivanova & Tarnopol'skii, 1994). Carrying out a Library Research provides many benefits for a researcher, including providing the opportunity to demonstrate closeness and understanding of the research topic to be conducted, developing the theoretical framework and research methodology that will be used, positioning oneself as an expert researcher who has the ability to conduct research and master each stage, and show the public the benefits of the research carried out and how this research can overcome gaps or provide solutions to problems (Cahyono et al., 2019).

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The object of the research is the influence of microeconomic variables. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on the influence of microeconomic variables.

The source of data collection comes from searching national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Sinta, and Scopus via the Perish/Harzing application. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word "Microeconomics" within the entire year period (1982-2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals that have been published collected the data; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics based on Library Research studies (Budianto, 2023) (Gozali et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rofika et al., 2023) (Budianto,

FEB Student Scientific Journal	6
EKSYA: Journal of Sharia Economics, Scientific Journal of Islamic Economics	5
Journal of Economic Education (JUPE), JUKRAMI: Journal of Education	4
Economy	
Economist: Journal of Science	Economics and Development Studies,
	3
PERFORMANCE	
Angricultural Socio-Economic Journal, Al-MAQASHID, Analysis Agricultural Policy, Bharanomic, Diponogoro Law Journal, Journal Theoretical and Applied Sharia Economics, Encyclopedia of Journals, Inovbiz:	
Journal of Business Innovation, IQTISHADUNA, J-ABDI: Journal of Service	
To the community, JEHSS: Journal of Education, Humanities and Social Sciences (JEHSS), JAMIE: Journal of Community Service for Economic Sciences,	
Abdidas Journal, PROFIT: Journal of Business Administration, Journal of Administration	2
Public, Akunsyah Journal: Journal of Sharia Accounting and Finance,	
Dinamik: Journal of Management Dynamics, JIBAKU: Journal of Business and Accounting, Scientific Journal of Management and Business, Journal of Management STIE Palopo, Journal of Insan Mandiri Education, Kodifikasia, Media Ekonomi, Maro: Journal of Sharia Economics and Business, An-Nisbah, MIMBAR, Monetar: Journal of Accounting and Finance, Methosika.	

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 3 shows the most productive researchers, namely: Jairin from STIS AL-ITTIHAD Bima, who wrote 5 articles.

Table 3. Researcher Productivity related to Microeconomics	
Researcher	Amount Publication
Jairin (STIS AL-ITTIHAD Bima)	5
Abdul Haris (Teacher at Cirebon College of Economics)	3
Mujiono (Department of Business Administration, Administration Study Program Bengkulu State Polytechnic Business), Eka Travilta Oktaria (Faculty Business, Indonesian Partner University)	2

microfinance institution, part, percent, performance, farmers, poverty, ratio, sector, social performance, used sp.

- Cluster 4, yellow is formed from 19 items, namely: ability, amount, bank, benefit, concept, cost, customer, economy, effort, field, financing, fund, gdp, last tax load, person, problem, source, success, term.
- Cluster 5, purple is formed from 15 items, namely: company, der, effect, factor, food, inflation, interest rate, productivity, rate, return, roe, significant effect, stock return, value, variable.
- Cluster 6, turquoise blue is formed from 15 items, namely: activity, business, community, condition, documentation, empowerment, existence, form, interview, lack, observation, role, village, welfare, worker.
- Cluster 7, orange is formed from 10 items, namely: assistance, covid, implementation, abstacle, pandemic, paper, place, policy, provision, researcher.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Factors that Influence Microeconomic Variables

Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, researchers found 60 factors that influence microeconomic variables, that is:

(1) Tax. Taxes have a significant influence on Microeconomics. Taxes can influence consumer decisions in purchasing goods and services, as well as producers' decisions in determining prices and production. Taxes can also affect investment decisions and business growth. If taxes are too high, consumers may reduce spending and producers may reduce production, which could have a negative impact on the microeconomy.

(2) The role of women. The role of women in the economy also has a significant influence on Microeconomics. Women have an important role in the production, trade and consumption of goods and services. Women's involvement in the economy can increase productivity and family income, as well as reduce poverty. In addition, increasing access and employment opportunities for women can encourage economic growth and help strengthen the microeconomy.

(3) Potential regional economic resources. The potential of regional economic resources has an important influence on microeconomics. Regional economic resources such as natural resources, labor, and infrastructure can influence production levels and the ability of local businesses to compete with global markets. If regional economic resources are utilized well, this can increase productivity and microeconomic growth.

(4) Patterns of developing people's economic posts. The pattern of developing people's economic posts also has an influence on microeconomics. People's economic posts can provide access to a wider market and improve the skills and quality of products produced by micro and small businesses. Apart from that, people's economic posts can also help micro and small business actors to gain access to capital and expand market reach, which can help increase the growth and development of micro businesses.

(5) Impact of integrated livestock and food agriculture projects. The impact of integrated livestock and food agriculture projects also has an influence on microeconomics. This integrated project can increase agricultural and livestock production, as well as increase market access for the products produced. This can provide opportunities for micro and small businesses to increase their production and income. In addition, this project can also improve food security and provide access to healthier food for the community, which can help improve the overall well-being and health of the community.

(6) The measure of economic mass as a measure of inertia. Economic life span measures how long a productive asset can last before it becomes obsolete or no longer effective. The longer the economic life of an asset, the smaller its inertia. Inertia refers to the ability of an economy to respond quickly to changes in demand or supply. If the assets owned have a long economic life, then the inertia of an economy will be lower because these assets can be used for a long time without needing to be replaced with new ones.

(7) Poverty. Poverty can affect the economy negatively because people living in poverty do not have enough access to resources and opportunities. This can hinder their ability to create and maintain businesses, increase productivity, and consume goods and services that can increase demand and economic growth.

(8) Economic law. Economic laws are the principles that govern economic behavior, such as the law of supply and demand and the law of profit. Economic laws influence the behavior of individuals, companies, and governments in making economic decisions. If economic laws are implemented well, they can increase the efficiency and effectiveness of the economy.

(9) Differences in Conventional versus Islamic Economic Paradigms. The conventional economic paradigm focuses on creating profits and economic growth, while the Islamic economic paradigm considers moral and social aspects in making economic decisions. The Islamic economic paradigm also avoids usury (interest), speculation, and economic practices that are considered detrimental to society.

(10) Conducive investment climate. A conducive investment climate can help encourage microeconomic growth. This can be achieved by providing tax incentives and subsidies, creating a stable and transparent business environment, and increasing access to resources such as capital and technology. The more conducive the investment climate is, the more small and medium businesses can develop and contribute to the economy.

(11) Social performance and financial performance. Social performance and financial performance can influence microeconomics in several ways. Companies or organizations that succeed in maintaining good social performance, such as providing benefits to society, can gain support and trust from consumers and stakeholders, which can improve their reputation and financial performance.

(12) Empowering the productive economic potential of society. Empowering society's productive economic potential can influence microeconomics by increasing society's ability to create and generate wealth. This can lead to increased income and improved overall well-being of society, and can provide opportunities for companies to reach larger markets.

(13) Productivity and profitability. Productivity and profitability are very important in microeconomics, because companies must produce quality and efficient products or services in order to remain competitive and achieve good profits. High levels of productivity and profitability can strengthen a company's competitiveness and provide benefits for stakeholders.

(14) Economic justice. Economic justice can influence microeconomics by providing equal opportunities for everyone to participate in the market. Economic justice can increase people's involvement in the economy, which can help reduce social inequality and promote sustainable economic growth.

(15) Social function. Social functioning can also influence microeconomics in the same way as economic justice. Good social functions can help create a stable and attractive business environment, which can increase societal prosperity and

corporate success. This can help create a wider market and increase access to new business opportunities.

(16) Economic reconstruction. Economic reconstruction can affect microeconomics by changing the overall business climate. If economic reconstruction is successful in building confidence among investors and consumers, this could increase demand and economic growth at the micro level. In addition, appropriate fiscal and monetary policies in economic reconstruction can encourage micro and small businesses to develop and create new jobs.

(17) Brand policy. Brand policy can influence microeconomics by creating added value to the products or services offered by the company. A strong and trusted brand can increase the value and selling price of a product, which in turn can increase company revenue and profits. This can encourage companies to hire more employees and improve welfare at a micro level.

(18) Business competency. Business competency can influence microeconomics by increasing company efficiency and productivity. Competent businesses can produce products or services at lower costs, increasing profits and competitiveness. This can help micro and small businesses survive in a competitive market and can improve welfare at the micro level.

(19) The role of the Sharia Banking system. The role of the Islamic banking system in microeconomics is to provide a cheap source of funding for micro and small businesses. With the existence of a sharia banking system, micro and small businesses can access financing on more affordable terms. This can help micro and small businesses to grow and develop, and ultimately improve prosperity at the micro level.

(20) The role of students. The role of students in microeconomics can be seen in the form of innovation and entrepreneurship. Students can become new entrepreneurs who create jobs, or can increase the efficiency of existing micro and small businesses. Apart from that, innovation carried out by students can spur economic growth at the micro level by creating new products or services that produce added value.

(21) Legal development. Legal development can have a positive impact on microeconomics because it can create legal stability and certainty for business actors. This can increase investor confidence and facilitate the investment and business planning process. Thus, legal development can contribute to increased economic activity and overall economic growth.

(22) Legal protection. Legal protection can also have a positive impact on microeconomics because it provides protection to business actors from illegal or unfair actions from other parties. This can help create a more stable business climate and better encourage economic activity.

(23) Revolving loan funds. Revolving loan funds can help small and medium businesses gain access to capital. With these funds, business actors can obtain capital at lower interest rates, thereby reducing capital costs. In the long term, this can help increase economic growth and create new jobs.

(24) Local wisdom. Local wisdom can help create jobs and improve the welfare of local communities. Developing local potential such as cultural, culinary and tourism products can become a new source of income for local communities and open up new investment opportunities for business actors.

(25) Business strategic analysis. Business strategic analysis can help business actors evaluate their business performance and develop more effective business strategies. This can help them to gain greater profits and increase competitiveness in the market. In the long term, this can help increase economic growth.

(26) Profit sharing investment. Profit sharing investment can provide greater profits for investors and business actors if successful. This can help increase market liquidity and develop new investments in potential sectors. In the long term, profit-sharing investments can help increase economic growth by increasing access to capital and creating new jobs.

(27) Product protection. Product protection is a policy or law designed to protect consumers from defective or dangerous products. This policy can have a positive impact on microeconomics because it can increase consumer confidence and strengthen relationships between consumers and producers. With strong product protection, consumers will feel safer and more comfortable in purchasing products, which in turn can increase product demand and sales. This can help encourage microeconomic growth.

(28) Franchise agreement. A franchise agreement is an agreement between two parties where the first party gives the second party the right to use a trademark or business system that has been developed by the first party. The impact of a franchise agreement on microeconomics can vary depending on the quality and attractiveness of the trademark or business system provided by the first party to the second party. If the trademark or business system has high appeal and is of good quality, then Franchise agreements can increase the productivity and efficiency of second party businesses, which in turn can increase microeconomic growth.

(29) The role of social aspects. The role of social aspects includes factors such as corporate social responsibility, fairness in business relationships, and the role of society in economic development. The role of social aspects can have a positive impact on microeconomics, especially in the long term. When a company has good social responsibility, for example in terms of the environment or worker welfare, this can improve the company's image and increase public trust in the company. In addition, when the community is involved in the economic development process, this can increase participation and involvement in the economic development process, which in turn can increase microeconomic growth.

(30) Sharia Financing. Sharia financing is a type of financing that is based on the principles of Islamic sharia. The impact of Sharia financing on microeconomics depends on the type of financing used and how the financing is carried out. However, in general, Sharia financing can increase access to finance for small businesses and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) which may find it difficult to obtain financing from conventional financial institutions. This can help increase the growth of SMEs and the micro economy as a whole. In addition, Sharia financing can also help encourage socially and environmentally responsible business practices, which in turn can increase trust and business image.

(31) Economic empowerment of the people. Community economic empowerment, such as providing training and business capital to underprivileged communities, can increase the number and quality of micro-entrepreneurs in an area. This can have a positive impact on local economic growth and create new jobs, which can strengthen the micro-economy in the area.

(32) Financial literacy. Financial literacy can increase people's understanding of financial management, including the importance of saving, managing debt, investing and insurance. By having sufficient knowledge about

finance, people can make wiser decisions in managing their finances, and reduce financial risks that can have an impact on the microeconomy.

(33) The Role of the Waqf Board. The Waqf Board can play an important role in supporting microeconomic development. Through the establishment of training and business incubation centers, the Waqf Board can help communities build the business skills and knowledge needed to manage their micro-enterprises. In addition, by providing business capital and technical support, the Waqf Board can help poor people start sustainable micro-enterprises.

(34) Monthly turnover. The monthly turnover of micro businesses can be an important indicator of the health of the micro economy. The higher the monthly turnover, the healthier the micro economy, because this shows that the micro business is able to meet market needs and generate sufficient profits to survive. In the long term, monthly turnover growth can help micro businesses to grow and develop.

(35) Revolving loans (BUMDES). Revolving loans from BUMDES can help poor people gain access to the business capital needed to start or expand their micro businesses. This can increase the number and quality of micro businesses in an area, which in turn can strengthen the micro economy in that area.

(36) Social media. Social media can influence microeconomics in several ways. First, social media can help companies expand market reach and increase consumer engagement with customers. Second, social media can also provide an opportunity to build a brand and introduce new products and services. However, social media can also pose risks if used inappropriately or irresponsibly, such as spreading false information or generating negative sentiment that can be detrimental to the company.

(37) The role of cooperatives. Cooperatives can influence microeconomics by strengthening local economic strength and promoting community participation in economic activities. Cooperatives can help drive local economic development by providing access to resources and training for members, as well as increasing purchasing power through collective purchasing and price negotiations with suppliers.

(38) Infrastructure assistance. Infrastructure assistance such as roads, electricity networks and clean water networks can help increase efficiency and productivity in the micro economy. Adequate infrastructure can open access to a wider market and increase the competitiveness of local products. Infrastructure can also help create new jobs and improve the economic welfare of local communities.

(39) Economic behavior. Consumer and producer behavior can influence micro markets. For example, as more consumers buy a particular product, demand will increase and the price of the product may increase. On the other hand, as producers produce more of a product, supply may increase and prices may fall. Economic behavior can also influence investment decisions and business policies.

(40) Empowerment of waqf banks. Empowering waqf banks can help increase access to capital and increase community involvement in economic activities. Waqf banks can provide loans with low or no interest to support small and medium business activities. This can help strengthen the local economy and improve community welfare.

(41) MSMEs. MSMEs (Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises) have an important role in the micro economy, especially in terms of creating jobs and local economic growth. MSMEs also contribute to national income and social development.

In a market context, MSMEs can compete with large companies and strengthen competition in the market.

(42) Request a price balance offer. Demand supply equilibrium price is an important concept in microeconomics, because it determines the price and quantity produced in the market. If demand and supply are balanced, prices will be stable and markets will be efficient. However, if there are changes in demand or supply, price and quantity fluctuations can occur in the market.

(43) The role of LazisMU. LazisMU (Amil Zakat, Infaq and Shadaqah Society and Community) can contribute to the micro economy through the distribution of zakat, infaq and alms. This can help poor communities and can help develop micro businesses.

(44) Government policy. Government policies can have a significant impact on the microeconomy. Fiscal and monetary policies can influence economic activities, such as investment, consumption, and import-export. Regulatory policies can also affect the market, including MSMEs.

(45) Banking credit. Bank credit can be an important source of financing for MSMEs in starting or expanding their businesses. However, credit that is difficult to obtain or high interest rates can be an obstacle to the development of MSMEs. Therefore, credit availability and interest rate policies can influence the success of MSMEs.

(46) Family empowerment. Family empowerment can have a positive influence on microeconomics. If families are empowered with the skills and knowledge needed to start a small business or expand a business, this can increase family income and their contribution to the economy. Families who are able to manage their finances well can also help reduce poverty and socio-economic inequality.

(47) Consignment sales (wakalah bil ujah). Consignment sales or wakalah bil ujah is a financial mechanism that can help micro and small entrepreneurs to obtain capital. In this way, entrepreneurs can borrow capital from other parties (such as banks) by providing collateral for the goods sold in a wakalah bil ujah contract. If implemented well, this mechanism can help entrepreneurs micro and small to increase productivity and support local economic growth.

(48) The relevance of accounting standards. Accounting standards have an important influence in managing company finances, including micro and small companies. Accounting standards can help reduce the risk of financial fraud and increase transparency in financial reporting. This can enable investors and other parties to make better decisions regarding investments, partnerships, or other transactions with the company.

(49) Sharia Economic Law. Sharia Economic Law has a significant influence in guiding economic activities, including microeconomic activities. Within the legal framework of Sharia Economics, businesses conducted must comply with the principles of Islamic ethics and morality. This can help reduce the risk of fraud and ensure long-term business continuity.

(50) BAZNAS productive zakat. Productive zakat is a mechanism for allocating zakat to support economic activities, including the development of micro and small businesses. If done well, productive zakat can help increase productivity and economic independence for people in need. This can help in reducing poverty and increasing the contribution of the microeconomic sector to overall economic growth.

(51) Digital economy. The digital economy can have a significant impact on microeconomics because it can accelerate the growth of micro businesses, expand market reach, increase operational efficiency, and enable micro businesses to compete with large businesses. This is mainly due to technology's ability to connect micro businesses with potential customers and business partners around the world.

(52) Micro entrepreneur productivity. The productivity of micro entrepreneurs can have a positive impact on the microeconomy because it can increase income, business growth and job creation at the local level. Higher productivity can also help micro businesses to compete in increasingly tough markets and improve the quality of their products and services.

(53) Relevance, Utility and Maslahah. The concepts of relevance, utility, and benefit can help micro businesses to develop products and services that better suit the needs and desires of their customers. This can help micro businesses to attract more customers, increase revenue and strengthen their position in the market.

(54) Take over microfinance. The take over of microfinance can have both positive and negative impacts on the microeconomy. On the one hand, taking over micro financing can help micro businesses to access greater resources and develop more quickly. However, on the other hand, the take over of microfinance could trigger market consolidation, which could lead to less competition and a loss of product and service diversity.

(55) Baitul Maal wa Tamwiil/BMT. Baitul Maal wa Tamwiil (BMT) can help increase micro business actors' access to financing and strengthen the local economic base. BMT can also help encourage entrepreneurship and strengthen the capacity of micro entrepreneurs. With BMT, micro business people can obtain the funds needed to expand their business, develop new products and services, and increase their productivity. This can help increase economic growth at the local level and strengthen the microeconomic base.

(56) Demand and supply. The law of supply and demand is the basis of microeconomics. If demand increases, then the price and quantity of sales will increase. If supply increases, then the price and quantity sold will fall. Changes in demand and supply will influence production decisions and product prices, and can affect company profit levels and household income.

(57) Socio-Economic Resilience. The level of socio-economic security of an individual or household can influence spending and saving decisions. The higher it is the level of socio-economic security, the greater the likelihood that an individual or household will spend more money and save less.

(58) People's Business Credit/KUR Financing. KUR financing can influence micro business activities. If financing is available at low interest rates, micro businesses can obtain greater capital to develop their business. On the other hand, if financing is difficult to obtain, micro business activities can be hampered.

(59) Impact of the pandemic. Pandemics can affect microeconomics by affecting demand and supply, prices, and production decisions. In addition, the pandemic can also affect access to resources, such as capital and labor, which can affect a company's ability to produce goods and services.

(60) Changes in people's income. Changes in people's income can influence demand and supply, prices, and production decisions. If income increases, demand will increase and prices will tend to rise. Conversely, if income falls, then demand will fall and prices will tend to fall.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research on the Influences Caused by Microeconomic Variables

Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, researchers found 25 influences caused by microeconomic variables, that is:

(1) Company profits. Microeconomics has a significant influence on company profits. Through cost analysis, companies can identify costs related to production and make the right decisions in setting optimal selling prices for products and services. Additionally, through demand and supply analysis, companies can identify profitable markets and adjust production and marketing strategies accordingly.

(2) Socioeconomic changes in farmers. Microeconomics can influence farmers' socio-economic changes through market analysis. Farmers who are able to produce more efficient and quality products can make more money than farmers who are unable. Additionally, through supply and demand analysis, farmers can determine optimal prices for their products.

(3) Mining and mining service company share prices. Microeconomics influences share prices of mining and mining service companies through factors that influence company performance. Cost and income analysis can help investors assess the potential profits and risks of investing in mining and mining service companies. Additionally, factors such as changes in commodity prices, government regulations, and industry competition can also influence a company's stock price.

(4) Regional economic driver. Microeconomics can become a regional economic driver through business activities in the area. Through market analysis, companies can identify business opportunities in the area and increase their production and sales. Additionally, successful companies can attract more investment to the area and create more jobs.

(5) Rural economic development. Microeconomics can contribute to rural economic development through supply and demand analysis. Farmers and business people in rural areas can produce more efficient and quality products and determine optimal prices for their products. In addition, companies that utilize rural resources such as agriculture, livestock, or tourism can increase the income of local residents and improve the welfare of rural communities.

(6) MSMEs. Microeconomics plays an important role in the development of MSMEs because MSMEs are small business units and operate in narrower markets, and are often influenced by microeconomic factors such as demand, competition and regulations. Microeconomic concepts such as production costs, prices, and elasticity of demand can help MSME owners to make the right decisions regarding products and selling prices, marketing strategies, and financial and risk management.

(7) Economic performance. Microeconomics plays an important role in determining the economic performance of a country. Microeconomic concepts such as demand and supply, production and costs, as well as competition and monopoly can influence prices and output in the market, which in turn affects the level of inflation, economic growth and societal welfare. By understanding microeconomic concepts, governments and policy makers can take appropriate actions to improve overall economic performance.

(8) The value of the company. Microeconomic concepts such as decision theory and theory of the firm can help identify factors that influence a company's value, such as production costs, market demand, and the level of competition. In managing a company, management must consider these factors and decide on appropriate policies to maximize company value.

(9) Capital structure and company value. Capital structure, namely the composition of funding sources used by a company, can also be influenced by microeconomic factors such as cost of capital, risk, and availability of resources. Microeconomic concepts can help management in choosing the optimal capital structure to increase company value.

(10) Socioeconomic society. Microeconomics also plays an important role in understanding the relationship between economic and social factors in society. Microeconomic concepts such as distribution of income and wealth, social mobility, and economic inequality can help identify social and economic problems in society. By understanding these factors, governments and policy makers can take appropriate actions to improve the overall welfare of society.

(11) Economic growth rate. The rate of economic growth is influenced by various microeconomic factors, such as demand and supply in the market, company productivity and efficiency, and the level of investment and innovation. Efficient and productive companies can produce more goods and services, thereby increasing output and national income. In addition, appropriate investment in research and development and infrastructure can increase the productivity and efficiency of the economic sector, and ultimately accelerate the rate of economic growth.

(12) Islamic Economic Law. Islamic Economic Law talks about how to make transactions that are fair and do not harm both parties, as well as avoiding usury and speculation. These principles can influence the behavior of economic actors, both companies and individuals. Economic actors who apply these principles will tend to consider long-term interests and not only seek momentary profits. This can have a positive impact on economic stability and long-term growth.

(13) Performance of Rural Banks/BPR. The performance of Rural Banks/BPRs is greatly influenced by risk and liquidity management. Microeconomics plays an important role in determining credit risk and the ability of BPRs to manage their liquidity. Interest rates, monetary policy, and market conditions can also influence BPR performance. As a financial institution that focuses on providing credit to small and medium businesses, BPR can also influence economic growth by facilitating access to capital for this sector.

(14) Risks of stock investment in the food and beverage business sector. The risk of stock investment in the food and beverage business sector is influenced by various microeconomic factors, such as company performance and market competition. Companies in this sector that are efficient and able to produce quality products at competitive prices will tend to perform well and attract investor interest. However, this sector is also vulnerable to changes in government policies, changes in consumer lifestyles, and changes in raw materials and production costs, which can affect company performance and investment risks.

(15) Economic growth rate. The rate of economic growth is influenced by various microeconomic factors, including corporate productivity and efficiency, investment, regulations, and market conditions. Efficient and productive companies can produce more goods and services, thereby increasing output and national income. Appropriate investments in research and development and infrastructure can increase the productivity and efficiency of economic sectors, and ultimately accelerate the rate of economic growth. Regulations that promote healthy competition and reduce production costs can also accelerate economic growth.

(16) Food and beverage stock prices. Food and beverage stock prices are influenced by microeconomic factors such as demand and supply, production costs, product innovation, competition, and government regulations. If demand for food and beverages increases, the share prices of companies operating in this sector will likely

rise. Likewise, if production costs fall, the company's share price can increase due to the potential for greater profits.

(17) Cracker management center. Cracker management centers are also influenced by the same microeconomic factors such as demand and supply, production costs, competition, and government regulations. If there is an increase in demand for crackers, the price of raw materials needed such as tapioca flour and cooking oil is likely to rise, which could affect the selling price and potential profits of the cracker management center.

(18) LQ45 shares. LQ45 shares are a stock index consisting of the 45 best companies in Indonesia selected based on certain criteria. LQ45 share prices are influenced by microeconomic factors such as the performance of the companies included in the index, market conditions and competition in each company's sector, as well as government regulations and policies that affect the industry in which the company operates.

(19) Profitability of Sharia People's Financing Banks/BPRS. The profitability of Sharia Rural Banks/BPRS is influenced by microeconomic factors such as economic growth, financial market conditions, risk management, portfolio quality, and competition with other banks in the same sector. If economic growth increases, Islamic banks will have greater opportunities to channel financing and earn profits.

(20) JII share price. JII (Jakarta Islamic Index) share prices are influenced by microeconomic factors such as the performance of companies listed on the index, market conditions and competition in each company's sector, as well as government regulations and policies that affect the industry in which the company operates. Apart from that, macroeconomic factors such as interest rate policies and global financial market conditions can also influence JII share prices.

(21) returns. Stock returns are influenced by microeconomic factors such as company performance, market conditions and competition in the same sector, as well as government regulations and policies that affect the industry in which the company operates. Internal company factors such as financial management, risk management, product innovation and operational efficiency can also influence stock returns.

(22) Sharia Commercial Bank capital structure. The capital structure of Islamic Commercial Banks is influenced by microeconomic factors such as bank performance, financial market conditions, government regulations and policies, as well as the characteristics of the Islamic banking industry. Capital structure can influence the risks and profits generated by a bank, as well as influence the bank's ability to meet customer financing needs.

(23) Non Performing Financing /NPF at Sharia Commercial Banks. NPF at Sharia Commercial Banks is influenced by microeconomic factors such as bank risk management, quality of financing portfolio, economic conditions, as well as government regulations and policies. If a bank's risk management is ineffective, portfolio quality is poor, or economic conditions worsen, it is likely that the NPF will increase.

(24) Poverty alleviation. Poverty alleviation is influenced by microeconomic factors such as access to education and training, employment opportunities, access to markets and resources, as well as government policies that support poverty alleviation. These factors can help increase the ability of individuals and community groups to increase income and reduce poverty levels.

(25) Zakat collection. Zakat collection is influenced by microeconomic factors such as public perception and awareness about zakat obligations, government policies that support zakat collection, and the governance of zakat institutions. If people are more aware of their zakat obligations and the government supports zakat collection through policies and programs, then zakat collection can increase. Apart from that, good and effective governance at zakat institutions can also influence the level of zakat collection.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- The number of research publications regarding the influence of microeconomic variables during the period 1982 to 2022 shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 323 research articles, which come from international journals indexed by Scopus, international journals and national journals indexed by Sinta.
- The affiliate/institution that publishes the most research results is the Student Online Journal (JOM) for Agriculture, which is the institution that publishes the most journals that publish results on Microeconomics, with a total of 8 journal publications.
- The most productive researcher in publishing research results is Jairin from STIS AL-ITTIHAD Bima, who wrote 5 articles.
- In the mapping visualization using VOSviewer, research developments regarding the influence of Microeconomic variables are divided into 7 clusters and 154 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 38 topics, cluster 2 consists of 33 topics, cluster 3 consists of 24 topics, cluster 4 consists of 19 topics, cluster 5 consists of 15 topics, cluster 6 consists of 15 topics, and cluster 7 consists of 10 topics.
- Based on the Library Research, there are 2 main research themes surrounding the influence of Microeconomic variables, namely: (1) Factors that influence Microeconomic variables, with a total of 60 factors; and (2) Influence caused by Microeconomic variables, with a total of 25 influences.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- the Library Research study can be explained in a more complex way.

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